

22NRM01 TraMeXI

D7 - Draft B comparison report for supplementary comparison for air kerma calibrations in X-ray imaging reference radiation qualities with specified uncertainties is submitted to EURAMET TC IR

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: VSL

Due date of the deliverable: 05-2026

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 05-2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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**METROLOGY
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Glossary

CMC	Calibration and measurement capability
KCDB	BIPM key comparison database
RQR	General radiography reference radiation qualities defined in IEC standard IEC 61267
RQT	Computed tomography reference radiation qualities defined in IEC standard IEC 61267
XMM	X-ray multimeter

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1 Summary

EURAMET supplementary comparison (EURAMET.RI(I)-S21) was conducted to assess the calibration and measurement capabilities of ten European national metrology laboratories for air kerma quantity relevant to medical x-ray imaging [1b]. The comparison was performed between November 2024 and December 2025. Two ionization chambers served as transfer instruments for air kerma. The comparisons covered conventional RQR and RQT radiation qualities [2], supplemented by newly developed copper filtered qualities, designed to extend traceability to higher filtration conditions representative of modern clinical practice [3].

Because no BIPM key comparisons exist for the radiation qualities included, no degrees of equivalence were determined [4, 5]. Instead, comparison reference values were established as the weighted mean of results from participants utilizing primary measurement methods. Traceability was based on free-air ionization chambers. The behaviour of the transfer instruments, including their stability during transport, was evaluated through repeated measurements at the pilot laboratory.

For EURAMET.RI(I)-S21, air kerma, the results show consistency across all radiation qualities, with all participants achieving $|E_n| \leq 1$. Overall, the comparisons confirm that the participating laboratories have capabilities to provide reliable and comparable calibration services for air kerma. The results support the maintenance or establishment of CMC entries in the KCDB [6]. The comparison results demonstrate the laboratories' capabilities across an expanded range of radiation qualities.

2 Proof of submission

The comparison report has been sent to the EURAMET TC-IR chair (Figure 1). The comparison report will be reviewed following the CCRI rules and when approved, it will be published in the KCDB.

Supplementary comparison report EURAMET.RI(I)-S20 and -S21

The screenshot shows an email interface. On the left, there is a profile picture of Toroi Paula (STUK) with a green checkmark, and the text 'Toroi Paula (STUK)' and 'To: Persson, Linda'. To the right of the profile are three buttons: 'Reply', 'Reply All', and 'Forward', followed by a three-dot menu icon. Below the profile information is a draft attachment box containing a PDF icon, the filename 'DRAFT_B_EURAMET.RI(I)-S20-S21.pdf', and the size '1 MB'. In the top right corner, the text 'pe 29.5.2026 8.46' is visible.

Dear Linda,

I am happy to send you, as the TC-IR chair, the report covering the supplementary comparisons on tube voltage, EURAMET.RI(I)-S20 and air kerma, EURAMET.RI(I)-S21. These comparisons are linked to the TraMeXI project. All participants have reviewed and agreed with the report. We have made our best to bring it to a good level, and we hope that you will find it acceptable. Could you please confirm receipt of the report? We would also be grateful for any comments or requests you may have.

Best regards,
Paula

Figure 1. The comparison report was sent by email to the EURAMET TC-IR chair for approval.

References

- [1] EURAMET.RI(I).S21 2026. <https://www.bipm.org/kcdb/comparison?id=1972> (accessed May 7, 2026).
- [2] International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). Medical diagnostic X-ray equipment - Radiation conditions for use in the determination of characteristics, IEC 61267:2025. 2025.
- [3] Krzanovic N, Toroi P, Komatina I, Jansen B, Boziari A, Caldeira M, de Castro M C, Ciccotelli A, Fernandes A, Kojic A, Lee K, Lindholm C, Pojtinger S, Reyhanoglu E, Rinaldi L, Sabeta A, Salomon E, Saroka S, Silvestri C, Sochor V, Valkama V, Vlahovic J and Zivanovic M. 2026 X-ray imaging dosimeter performance in standard and non-standard radiography radiation fields in terms of air kerma. Phys Med 2026;141:105687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2025.105687>.
- [4] CIPM. Measurement comparisons in the CIPM MRA, CIPM MRA-D-05. Sèvres, Paris: 2016.
- [5] EURAMET. Guide No. 4: Guide on comparisons. Braunschweig: 2021.
- [6] BIPM. KCDB The BIPM Key Comparison Database is available online 2019. <https://www.bipm.org/kcdb/> (accessed May 6, 2019).